

LEARNERS' MOTIVATION AS A MODERATING VARIABLE IN THE RELATIONSHIP OF TEACHING STRATEGIES AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF LEARNERS IN MULTIGRADE SCHOOLS IN THE THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates learners' motivation as a moderating variable in the relationship between teaching strategies and academic performance. Employing a quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design, data were gathered from 49 multigrade teachers and 299 learners using a structured survey questionnaire. The analysis reveals that while learners demonstrate strong intrinsic motivation, particularly in independence, responsibility, and classroom engagement, they also experience challenges such as difficulty concentrating and anxiety when learning alongside older peers. Teachers report using a variety of instructional strategies, with cooperative learning, inquiry-based approaches, and project-based learning identified as the most effective, whereas debate, homework, and field trips are less frequently implemented due to logistical limitations. Academic performance data show the majority of students performing at a "Satisfactory" level, with no learners reaching the "Outstanding" category. Correlation analysis indicates a weak and statistically non-significant relationship between learners' academic performance, motivation, and the teaching strategies employed. These findings suggest that although motivation and teaching strategies independently play roles in shaping academic outcomes, their interaction does not significantly enhance performance in this context. In response, an intervention program titled "Empowering Teachers: Effective Motivational Tools for Enhancing Student

Engagement” was developed to provide teachers with practical strategies aimed at boosting learner motivation and engagement in multigrade classrooms.

Keywords: *Learners’ Motivation, Teaching Strategies, Academic Performance, Multigrade Classrooms, Descriptive-Correlational Design, Student Engagement, Educational Intervention*

INTRODUCTION

Multigrade teaching refers to a classroom setup where a single teacher is responsible for instructing students from multiple grade levels, often comprising learners of varying ages and developmental stages. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) aims to ensure equitable access to quality education for all Filipino children. In response to the educational disparities in geographically isolated and underserved areas, the Department implemented DepEd Order No. 81, s. 2009, also known as the Multigrade Education Program (MEP), which seeks to optimize limited resources while promoting educational inclusivity. Despite these goals, multigrade teachers continue to face significant challenges, particularly in maintaining learner motivation, ensuring effective teaching practices, and improving academic performance in such complex learning environments.

Recent literature has highlighted the growing attention on multigrade education and its implications (Cornish, 2021). While existing studies recognize the role of learner motivation in shaping academic outcomes, debates persist on its exact influence in multigrade settings. Motivation is a critical component of educational success, as it enhances learner engagement, resilience, and achievement (Meng, 2023). However, sustaining high levels of motivation in multigrade classrooms remains difficult due to the diversity of learners’ age groups and needs. As Ozansoy (2022) observed, low motivation may result in reduced student participation and poor academic outcomes, undermining the objectives of the MEP.

Motivating learners is one of the most demanding yet essential aspects of teaching, especially in multigrade contexts (Ruiz, 2020). Teachers often struggle to align instructional strategies with varied academic goals, given the wide spectrum of abilities within a single class. Enhancing teaching strategies is therefore crucial, as they can significantly influence learners’ motivation and performance. Tan (2021) emphasized that multigrade teaching requires adaptable and innovative approaches due to the need for differentiated instruction. Without this flexibility, teachers may be overwhelmed by the demands of lesson preparation and classroom management, leading to reduced instructional effectiveness. Bruce (2020) similarly noted that academic performance in multigrade classrooms often suffers from the challenges of managing a heterogeneous group of learners, while Bua and Martin (2020) argued that the lack of focused instruction and appropriate resources widens the gap between multigrade and single-grade learners. Naparan and Alinsug (2021) also found that older students in multigrade settings may

lose interest when lessons repeat familiar content, making it difficult for teachers to maintain discipline and attention across grade levels.

Although previous research has examined the role of teaching strategies and their impact on academic performance, few studies have explored how learner motivation moderates this relationship, particularly in multigrade settings. Much of the existing literature focuses on single-grade environments, overlooking the complexities of teaching in multigrade classrooms with diverse learning profiles. This gap is especially relevant in the context of multigrade schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, where teachers face unique instructional challenges. The researchers of this study, as practicing multigrade teachers in the district, observed firsthand the difficulty in maintaining student motivation and ensuring consistent academic outcomes. Investigating motivation as a moderating variable could provide essential insights for developing more effective teaching strategies and educational interventions tailored to multigrade learning environments.

Given these observations and gaps in the literature, this study aims to examine learner motivation as a moderating variable in the relationship between teaching strategies and academic performance among students in multigrade schools. Addressing this issue is both timely and critical for informing more responsive and equitable educational policies and practices.

Research Questions

This study's primary goal was to determine the learners' motivation as a moderating variable in the relationship between teaching strategies and learners' academic performance in Multigrade schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learners' level of motivation in the Multigrade schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon?
2. What teaching strategies are employed by the teachers of Multigrade schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon?
3. What is the learners' academic performance in the Multigrade schools of the Third Congressional District of Quezon?
4. Does learners' motivation mediate the relationship between teaching strategies and academic performance?
5. Based on the study's findings, what intervention program could be formulated by the researcher?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design to examine the role of learner motivation as a moderating variable in the relationship

between teaching strategies and academic performance in multigrade classrooms. The research was conducted in the Third Congressional District of Quezon Province (Bondoc Peninsula), a geographically remote region where multigrade education is widely implemented due to low student enrollment and limited resources.

A total of 49 multigrade teachers were selected through purposive sampling, limited to those with at least three years of experience, while 299 learners were chosen using random sampling to ensure representativeness. Data were collected using a researcher-made questionnaire comprising three sections: teaching strategies (13 items), learner motivation (16 items), and academic performance (self-reported grades). Items in the first two sections were rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The instrument underwent expert validation and pilot testing, yielding a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87, indicating high reliability.

With approval from the Department of Education, data were gathered through online surveys (Google Forms), distributed via secure links and QR codes to accommodate the respondents' remote locations. Ethical considerations such as informed consent and confidentiality were strictly observed.

The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, rankings) and multiple regression analysis to explore the relationships among variables and assess the moderating effect of motivation. While the study provides valuable insights into multigrade education dynamics, it is limited to a specific region, and its reliance on self-reported academic data may affect accuracy. Additionally, causality cannot be inferred due to the non-experimental design.

RESULTS

Part I. Learners' Level of Motivation in the Multigrade Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Table 1

Learners' Level of Motivation in the Multigrade Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

	Indicators	Mode	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Mas madali akong matuto sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil nakikita ko kung paano tinuturuan ang mga mas nakababatang mag-aaral.	4	Highly Motivated
2.	Mas nagiging malaya at responsable ako sa pag-aaral ko sa mga klase sa maraming baitang.	5	Extremely Motivated
3.	Mas marami akong natututunan tungkol sa iba't ibang kultura at pananaw sa mga klase sa maraming baitang.	4	Highly Motivated
4.	Mas madaling maunawaan ang mga konsepto sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil paulit-ulit na natututunan ko ang mga ito.	5	Extremely Motivated
5.	Mas nakakahanap ako ng mga kaibigan na may iba't ibang edad sa mga klase sa maraming baitang.	5	Extremely Motivated

6.	Mas nagiging masigasig ako sa pag-aaral sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil mas nakaka-engganyo ang mga aralin.	5	Extremely Motivated
7.	Nakatutulong sa akin na mas maanalisa ang aking aralin habang ang aking guro ay nagtuturo sa ibang level.	5	Extremely Motivated
8.	Mahirap para sa akin na maunawaan ang mga aralin sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil iba-iba ang antas ng mga mag-aaral.	4	Highly Motivated
9.	Mahirap para sa akin na makuha ang atensyon ng guro sa mga klase sa maraming baitang.	1	Not Motivated at all
10.	Mahirap para sa akin na magtanong ng mga katanungan sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil nahihya ako sa mga mas nakatatandang mag-aaral.	5	Extremely Motivated
11.	Nakakaramdam ako ng kaba sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil kailangan kong makipagsabayan sa mas nakatatandang mag-aaral.	1	Not Motivated at all
12.	Mahirap para sa akin na mag-focus sa pag-aaral sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil mas maingay.	5	Extremely Motivated
13.	Nakakaramdam ako ng pagkabalisa sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil mas maraming mag-aaral.	5	Extremely Motivated
14.	Mahirap para sa akin na mag-aral nang mabuti sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil mas mabagal ang takbo ng mga aralin.	5	Extremely Motivated
15.	Mahirap para sa akin na makisabay sa mga kapwa ko mag-aaral sa mga klase sa maraming baitang dahil mas maraming gawain.	5	Extremely Motivated
16.	Mas gusto ko ang mga klase sa iisang baitang kaysa sa mga klase sa maraming baitang.	1	Not Motivated at all

Part II. Teaching Strategies Employed by the Teachers of Multigrade Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon

Table 2

Teaching Strategies Employed by the teachers of Multigrade schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon

	Teaching Strategy	Mode	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Cooperative Group Learning	5	Always Employed
2.	Debate	2	Rarely Employed
3.	Demonstration / Modeling	5	Always Employed
4.	Discovery / Inquiry-based	5	Always Employed
5.	Field Trip	1	Never Employed
6.	Hands-on / Learn by Doing	5	Always Employed
7.	Homework	2	Rarely Employed
8.	Lecture	5	Always Employed
9.	Journal Writing	2	Rarely Employed
10.	Peer Tutoring	5	Always Employed
11.	Project-based Learning	5	Always Employed
12.	Self-directed Learning	5	Always Employed
13.	Simulation / Role-play	5	Always Employed
14.	Collaborative Planning	5	Always Employed
15.	Assessment for Learning	5	Always Employed
16.	Technology Integration	2	Rarely Employed
17.	Differentiated Instruction	2	Rarely Employed
18.	Gallery Walk	1	Never Employed
19.	Think-Pair-Share	1	Never Employed

Part III. Learners' Academic Performance in the Multigrade Schools of the Third Congressional District of Quezon

Table 3

Learners' Academic Performance in the Multigrade Schools of the Third Congressional District of Quezon

Category		Frequency	Rank
Satisfactory	(80%-84%)	273	1
Fairly Satisfactory	(75%-79%)	17	2
Very Satisfactory	(85%-89%)	9	3
Outstanding	(90%-100%)	0	4
Total		299	
Mean		81.88	
Standard Deviation		1.47	

Part IV. Correlation Analyses for the Moderating Effect of Learner's Motivation in the Relationship of Teaching Strategies and Academic Performance

Table 4

Correlation Analyses for the Moderating Effect of Learner's Motivation in the Relationship of Teaching Strategies and Academic Performance

		Correlations		
		Teachers' Teaching Strategies	Learners' Motivation	Learners' Academic Performance
Teachers' Teaching Strategies	Pearson Correlation	1	.133	.102
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.363	.486
	N	49	49	49
Learners' Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.133	1	-.123
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.363		.398
	N	49	49	49
Learners' Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.102	-.123	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.486	.398	
	N	49	49	49

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the motivation levels of learners in multigrade schools located in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. Among the motivation indicators assessed, the highest frequencies were observed in indicators 2, 4, 5, 6, and 7, all showing a mode of 5, indicating "Strongly Agree." These indicators suggest that learners in multigrade

settings feel more independent and responsible, benefit from repeated exposure to concepts, enjoy forming friendships with peers across grade levels, find lessons engaging, and can analyze lessons more effectively when the teacher is attending to another grade level. Similarly, indicators 8, 10, 12, 13, 14, and 15 also yielded a mode of 5. While these results imply strong agreement, they point toward notable challenges in the multigrade context, such as difficulties in understanding lessons due to varied learning levels, distractions caused by classroom noise, increased anxiety from larger class sizes, and difficulties with the pacing and volume of activities.

On the other hand, the lowest frequencies were recorded in indicators 9, 11, and 16, each having a mode of 1 or "Strongly Disagree." These responses indicate that learners generally do not experience significant challenges in attracting the teacher's attention, do not feel anxious about learning alongside older peers, and do not strongly prefer monograde over multigrade classes. While these concerns exist among some learners, the overall trend suggests that most students feel comfortable in multigrade environments and recognize the advantages they offer.

These findings align with Ainley (2021), who emphasized that motivation is a key driver of engagement and academic persistence. Motamedi (2020) supports this view, asserting that multigrade classrooms—when managed effectively—promote motivation through personalized instruction, peer support, and collaborative learning environments. In line with the results on repeated concept exposure (indicator 4), Ruiz (2020) highlighted the benefits of spaced learning, which enhances retention and deeper understanding. Moreover, Acatrinei and Popovici (2021) observed that multigrade settings foster inclusive learning communities, enabling students to form meaningful friendships across age groups, a finding reflected in the social interaction indicators of this study.

Conversely, challenges such as comprehension difficulties and classroom distractions—highlighted by lower agreement scores in some indicators—are consistent with the observations of Mnyandu (2020) and Meng (2023), who noted that diverse academic abilities and increased noise levels in multigrade classrooms can impact student focus and raise anxiety, particularly for younger or less confident learners. Ruiz (2020) further suggested that these challenges can be mitigated through adaptive teaching strategies that promote learner autonomy and equitable teacher attention.

Overall, the findings reveal that learners in multigrade schools across the Third Congressional District of Quezon demonstrate high motivation, driven by peer interaction, repeated concept reinforcement, and learner-centered instructional strategies. Although some issues persist—particularly concerning classroom noise, pacing, and varied learning levels—the general sentiment among students indicates a positive reception to the multigrade setup. These results suggest that with targeted teacher training and improved classroom management strategies, multigrade education can continue to support learner engagement and academic development effectively.

Table 2 presents the teaching strategies employed by teachers in multigrade schools within the Third Congressional District of Quezon, along with their corresponding frequency of use. The data indicates that the most frequently used strategies—rated as "5" or "Always Employed"—include Cooperative Group Learning,

Demonstration/Modeling, Discovery/Inquiry-Based Learning, Hands-On Learning/Learning by Doing, Lecture, Peer Tutoring, Project-Based Learning, Self-Directed Learning, Simulation/Role-Play, Collaborative Planning, and Assessment for Learning. These methods are predominantly interactive and student-centered, fostering collaboration, experiential learning, and independent inquiry. Their consistent use suggests that teachers find these strategies particularly effective in addressing the diverse needs and abilities inherent in multigrade classrooms.

In contrast, strategies such as Debate, Homework, Technology Integration, Differentiated Instruction, and Journal Writing are rarely employed. The infrequent use of Debate and Journal Writing may be attributed to time limitations and the complexity of facilitating these tasks across multiple grade levels. The minimal use of Homework suggests a preference for maximizing instructional time within the classroom, possibly to accommodate learners' varying access to support and resources at home.

Notably, Field Trips were rated as “1” or “Never Employed,” highlighting significant logistical and resource-related constraints that hinder their implementation. Factors such as remote school locations, limited funding, and challenges in ensuring student supervision may contribute to the impracticality of organizing such activities in multigrade settings.

These findings are consistent with previous research. Ozansoy (2022) emphasized that Cooperative Learning and Peer Tutoring significantly contribute to both social and academic development, making them well-suited for multigrade environments where cross-age collaboration is beneficial. Yip (2021) supported the use of Inquiry-Based and Experiential Learning in multigrade settings, arguing that such methods enhance student engagement and comprehension through active discovery and hands-on involvement—an approach well-aligned with the strategies frequently used by teachers in this study.

Conversely, the limited use of strategies such as Debate and Journal Writing mirrors findings by Shareefa (2020), who identified time constraints and classroom management challenges as barriers to implementing reflective or writing-intensive activities in multigrade contexts. Similarly, the absence of Field Trips reflects the insights of Taole (2022), who noted that rural and resource-limited schools often face difficulties in securing the necessary funds, transportation, and supervision for off-campus learning experiences.

The infrequent application of methods such as Gallery Walk and Think-Pair-Share may also be attributed to practical constraints. Romo (2021) observed that limited classroom space and the complexities of managing mixed-ability groups can inhibit the use of movement-based or partner activities in multigrade classrooms.

In summary, the findings suggest that teachers in multigrade schools prioritize interactive, student-centered strategies—particularly those that encourage collaboration and experiential learning—to effectively meet the diverse needs of their learners. Meanwhile, strategies that demand more time, resources, or individualized attention, such

as Debate, Journal Writing, and Field Trips, are used less frequently due to structural and logistical limitations inherent in the multigrade teaching context.

Table 3 presents the learners' academic performance in multigrade schools of the Third Congressional District of Quezon. As can be seen from the table, it revealed that most learners (274) achieved a “Satisfactory” performance level, making it the highest-ranking category. This suggests that most learners meet the expected learning competencies but may not excel beyond them. This result could indicate the effectiveness of the current teaching strategies in multigrade settings and highlight areas for improvement in fostering higher levels of academic achievement. The absence of learners in the “Outstanding” category is notable. This indicates a lack of exemplary academic performance among learners. Contributing to this could include limited access to resources, challenges in multigrade classroom management, or insufficient individualized support for high-achieving learners.

This finding aligns with Naparan and Alinsug's (2021) findings, which highlight that multigrade classrooms often face teacher overload and a lack of specialized training, which may impact the potential for exceptional academic outcomes. Nine learners (9) fall into the “Very Satisfactory” category, ranked 3, demonstrating that a small percentage of learners perform above average. Similarly, 17 learners are classified as “Fairly Satisfactory” (rank = 2), indicating that some learners are struggling but are performing at a minimally acceptable level. These figures highlight variability in the performance spectrum and suggest that differentiated instruction could help address the diverse needs of learners.

According to Potane (2020), multigrade classrooms often enable learners to achieve satisfactory levels of academic performance when teaching strategies and resources are aligned with the needs of multigrade learners. The study also highlights that learners in such settings frequently meet basic academic competencies, similar to the results of the Third Congressional District of Quezon, where “Satisfactory” is the dominant performance category.

In conclusion, most students in multigrade schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon performed at a “Satisfactory” level, indicating that they meet but rarely surpass fundamental competencies. The lack of “Outstanding” ratings indicates problems such as insufficient funding and a lack of tailored assistance. Even if some students did better or worse than expected, the findings show that tailored instruction is necessary to better meet the requirements of a wide range of learners and encourage higher academic accomplishment.

Table 4 presents the results of correlation analyses examining whether learners' motivation mediates between teaching strategies and academic performance. The Pearson correlation coefficient between teaching strategies and motivation is 0.133, indicating a weak positive correlation. However, the significance value (Sig.2-tailed) is 0.363, which exceeds the common threshold of 0.05, meaning this correlation is not statistically significant. This result suggests no strong or reliable relationship between teaching strategies and learners' motivation.

Similarly, the correlation between teaching strategies and academic performance is 0.102, showing a weak positive relationship. The significance value here is 0.486, also above 0.05, indicating that this relationship is not statistically significant. Therefore, no proof supports that the teaching strategies used have a meaningful impact on academic performance.

Furthermore, the correlation between learners' motivation and academic performance is -0.123, indicating a weak negative relationship. With a significant value of 0.398, this correlation is also not statistically significant. This suggests that learner motivation does not impact academic performance within this sample.

These findings revealed no significant relationships between teaching strategies, learners' motivation, and academic performance, implying that motivation does not moderate the relationship between teaching strategies and academic performance in the present situation.

A study by Tan (2021) emphasized that while teaching strategies can impact motivation, this effect often depends on external factors such as classroom environment and student background. In multigrade settings, when there are a variety of learning demands, general teaching strategies may have limited influence on motivation without tailored adjustments. This may explain the weak and non-significant correlation (0.133) between teaching strategies and motivation observed in this study.

The weak correlation between teaching strategies and academic performance (0.102) is consistent with findings by Lacre and Valle (2024), who argued that while student-centered strategies often improve engagement, their effect on Academic outcomes may not be immediate or directly measurable. Additionally, in complex multigrade environments, teaching strategies alone may not be sufficient to impact academic performance significantly without addressing individualized needs and learning support, which may dilute the impact observed in this analysis.

The lack of a significant correlation between motivation and academic performance (-0.123) also resonates with findings by Meng (2023), who suggested that motivation alone may not guarantee improved educational results, especially in multigrade contexts where learners' focus and learning levels vary widely. In such settings, performance may be influenced by factors beyond motivation, such as curriculum alignment, teacher-student ratios, and assessment methods.

Generally, the findings indicate that there is no significant relationship between academic performance, learner motivation, and teaching strategies in multigrade schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. This implies that the relationship between teaching strategies and academic performance is not mediated by motivation. Based to the poor connections, student outcomes in multigrade settings may be more significantly influenced by other factors, such as the classroom climate, individual support, and resource availability.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Learners in multigrade schools exhibit strengths and challenges in their motivation levels. While they demonstrate independence, responsibility, and engagement, they also struggle with concentration, understanding different levels of instruction, and anxiety related to peer comparison.
2. Teachers employ a diverse range of teaching strategies, with an emphasis on cooperative learning, inquiry-based instruction, and project-based learning. However, approaches such as debates, journal writing, and field trips are underutilized due to logistical constraints.
3. Despite the various strategies used, academic performance in multigrade schools remains mostly at the “Satisfactory” level, suggesting that while learners meet learning competencies, there is a need for additional interventions to help them excel further.
4. Weak but non-significant correlations among motivation, teaching strategies, and academic performance suggest that other factors may influence learners’ academic success. Thus, the result of the hypothesis is accepted.
5. Further research and continuous improvements in instructional strategies and motivational strategies are essential to optimizing learning outcomes in multigrade settings.

Recommendations

The following are suggested in light of the findings:

1. Learners in multigrade schools exhibit both strengths and challenges in terms of motivation. Teachers can enhance engagement and reduce anxiety through positive reinforcement, independent tasks, and peer support.
2. Since the result of the findings shows that some effective teaching strategies, such as debates, journal writing, and field trips, are underutilized due to logistical constraints, school administrators may provide additional resources and support to enable teachers to integrate these strategies into their instruction.
3. Since the study reveals that academic performance in multigrade schools remains mostly at the “Satisfactory” level, schools may implement enrichment programs such as remedial classes, peer tutoring, and supplementary learning materials to help learners excel beyond the minimum learning competencies.

4. Considering that the study was conducted at the beginning of the school year, the researcher developed an intervention program to equip teachers with innovative motivational techniques, classroom management skills, and technology integration strategies to enhance learners' motivation and engagement.
5. Future researchers may explore factors like socioeconomic status, parental involvement, and school resources to better understand student success in multigrade settings. Additionally, studies should collect data at different times in the academic year to capture more accurate trends in motivation, teaching strategies, and academic performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher of this study affirms that all ethical guidelines and research protocols were strictly followed throughout the investigation. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were also made aware of their right to withdraw from the study without penalty. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were maintained at all stages, and their well-being was prioritized and safeguarded. The research was conducted free from any conflicts of interest. Furthermore, the author(s) ensured that plagiarism was strictly avoided by properly acknowledging all sources used. The findings were interpreted objectively and without bias, and the results were utilized solely for academic and research purposes.

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REFERENCES

- Acatrinei, I. R., & Popovici, A. O. (2021). The organization of multigrade teaching in primary school: Challenges and chances. In Proceedings of the 14th International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation (pp. 1627–1633). Doi: 10.21125/iceri.2021.0442
- Ainley, M.H. (2021). Interest, Motivation and Achievement. In Handbook of Educational Psychology(pp.1-31). https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Azkananda-Widiasani/publication/310773130_Handbook_of_Student_Engagement/links/5836a0dd08aed45931c772b7/Handbook-of-Student-Engagement.pdf
- Bruce, T. (2020). Multigrade teaching in rural schools: A review of advances, practices, and challenges. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(1), 7-16. DOI:10.38124/ijisrt/IJSRT24JUN026
- Bua,J.D., & Martin, M.D.M.(2020). Handling multigrade teaching: Its educational implication towards teachers' competence. *Management Research Journal*, 9(2), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.37134/mrj.vol9.2.1.2020>
- Cornish, L (2021). Quality practices for multigrade teaching. University of the School of Education. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47381/aijre.v34i1.731>
- Lacre, D. H., & Valle, A. M. (2024). Classroom management practices and academic performance in multigrade classes. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 7(8), 3706–3711. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v7-i08-09>
- Meng, X.A. (2023). The relationship between student motivation and academic performance: The mediating role of online learning behavior. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 31(1), 167-180. DOI:10.1108/QAE-02-2022-0046
- Mnyandu, S. Z. (2020). Exploring teaching strategies used by teachers in multigrade classrooms in rural settings in the Umlazi District [Master Thesis, University of KwaZulu-Natal]. South Africa. <https://ukzn-dspace.ukzn.ac.za/handle/10413/19322>
- Motamedi, V. (2020). Comparative analysis of the results of multigrade and single grade classes based on indicators of educational productivity and efficiency: A case study of Bandar Abbas city primary and secondary school. *Journal of Education and Learning*. DOI: 10.11591/edulearn.v14i2.15871 <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1266600.pdf>
- Naparan, G., & Alinsug, V. (2021). Classroom strategies of multigrade teachers. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 3(1), 100109. DOI:10.1016/j.ssaho.2021.100109
- Ozansoy, J. J. (2022). The Impacts of Strategies in Teaching on Students' Performance in School. *Near East University Online Journal of Education - NEUJE*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.32955/neuje.v5i2.631>
- Potane, O. &. (2020). Opportunities and Challenges in Multigrade Teaching Using Direct and Indirect Teaching Methods with Zurashi and Watari Approaches in the

- Philippines: Kagay- Anon RIA Schools Experiences,
<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3652738>
- Romo, N. (2021). Multigrade Teaching Experiences in Ilocos Sur: Basis for Extension Program. The IAFOR International Conference on Education.
<https://doi.org/10.22492/issn.2189-1036.2021.31>
- Ruiz, J. P. (2020). Teacher Factors and Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupils in Baybay City Division: Inputs to an Improved Implementation of Multigrade Teaching. JPAIR Institutional Research, Volume 14. DOI:10.7719/irj.v14i1.801
- Shareefa, M. (2020). Using differentiated instruction in multigrade classes: a case of a small school. Asia Pacific Journal of Education, 1–15. LinkSEAMEO INNOTECH
- Tan, S. D. (2021). "Relationship between learning strategies and academic performance: a comparison between accreditation of prior experiential learning (APEL) and regular entry undergraduates" (Vol. Volume 16). Asian Association of Open Universities Journal.
<https://www.emerald.com/insight/publication/issn/1858-3431>
- Taole, M. (2022). Challenges encountered by teaching principals in rural multigrade primary schools: A South African perspective. (Vol. 18). 3: International Journal of Whole Schooling, <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1346705>
- Yip, M. (2021). The linkage among academic performance, learning strategies, and self-efficacy of Japanese university students: A mixed-method approach. Studies in Higher Education, 46(8), 1565-1577. DOI:10.1080/03075079.2019.1695111